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Methods of forming students' multicultural competence in English classes

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Annotation. Diversity of cultures is one of the characteristics of modern social life. Development of multicultural education in such an environment is an important task of education. This thesis examines the organization of educational processes in multicultural education by developing appropriate principles. In addition, while studying the theoretical and practical aspects of the methods of developing multicultural competence, the differences and similarities between them were considered.

Аннотация. Многообразие культур является одной из характеристик современной общественной жизни. Развитие поликультурного образования в такой среде является важной задачей образования. В диссертации рассматривается организация воспитательных процессов в поликультурном образовании путем разработки соответствующих принципов. Кроме того, при изучении теоретических и практических аспектов методов развития поликультурной компетентности были рассмотрены различия и сходства между ними.

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Annotatsiya. Madaniyatlarning turli xil bo'lishi zamonaviy ijtimoiy hayotning o'ziga xos xususiyatlaridan biridir. Bunday muhitda ko'p madaniyatli ta'limni rivojlantirish ta'limning muhim vazifasi hisoblanadi. Ushbu tezisda ko'p madaniyatli ta'limda o'ziga yarasha tamoyillarni ishlab chiqqan holda ta'lim jarayonlarini tashkil etishni ko'rib tadqiq etiladi. Bundan tashqari ko'p madaniyatli kompetensiyani rivojlantirish metodlarini nazariy va amaliy jihatlarini o'rganilgan holda ular o'rtasidagi farqli va o'xshash jihatlar ko'rib chiqildi.

Key words: multiculturalism, method, linguistics, communication, educational process, pedagogical activity.

Ключевые слова: мультикультурализм, метод, языкознание, общение, образовательный процесс, педагогическая деятельность.

Kalit so'zlar: multimadaniyat, metod, lingvistika, muloqot, ta'lim jarayoni, pedagogik faoliyat.

A multicultural educational environment can be characterized by a number of psychological characteristics, for example: intercultural communication, enrichment of the educational environment with cultural components, and preservation and development of cultural values in full diversity. These new requirements impose new requirements on the professional and pedagogical activity of future teachers.

Multicultural education aimed at ensuring the cultural and social identity of a person plays an important role in the formation of multicultural competence of a future specialist. Multicultural education ensures the involvement of future specialists in the discovery of national and world culture, and on this basis, the formation of the ability and readiness to live in a multinational environment. One of

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the main tasks of such education is to educate a person's spiritual culture, which is clearly manifested in the interaction of ethnophores (Ivaniuk, 2016).

Diversity of cultures is a characteristic feature of modern social life. The process of globalization, on the one hand, contributes to the enrichment of the cultures found in it; on the other hand, it can cause intercultural conflicts. Some scientists (T.G. Bogatyreva, T.G. Kiseleva, V.V. Krasnykh [36, p.17; 106; 119]) emphasize that there are positive and negative consequences of globalization. The authors argue that globalization can cause social instability and harm national and ethnic cultures. The high permeability of national borders, the increase in the intensity of cultural interaction is accompanied by a crisis of basic values, a change in the cultural context of the formation of cultural identity. This type of globalization can lead to the unification of cultures based on the principle of establishing the dominant position of the culture of a country that is economically superior to others. The reason for this is that often people are not ready to communicate with people who have different values, views, behavior. In this context, the inconsistency between people's cultural priorities leads to hostility towards the "alien", social aggression, and thus intolerance towards the other.

In addition, modern scientists L. L. Suprunova and A. Yu. Belogurov emphasized that it is important to ensure the following principles in multicultural education [1, p. 4],:

- the principle of globality of the cultural-educational process;
- the principle of multicultural tolerance and inter-educational perspective;
- the principle of self-awareness.

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One of the ways to form multiculturalism is the process of teaching a foreign language, which forms a desire to cooperate with representatives of other cultures, a tolerant attitude towards them, and preparation for intercultural communication.

It is effective to conduct training in various forms using active teaching methods for the formation of multicultural competence of future philologists in English language learning, in particular:

- conferences;
- quizzes on linguistic local studies;
- virtual trips to countries whose inhabitants speak English;
- debates and discussions;
- creative contests;
- presentations, projects;
- days and holidays of national culture.

In order to form the components of multicultural competence of future philologists, it is necessary to create educational communicative situations that determine the conditions and goals of communication for the organization of intercultural communication in English classes. In such lessons, topics related to the characteristics of the culture of different countries and peoples can be used. During the discussions in such lessons, the teacher should also implement the goals of multicultural education, students should be tolerant of representatives of other cultures, as well as their traditions, religion, customs, norms, and not their language. should form a relationship. public morals and ethics.

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The English language teaching system is an effective environment for the formation of multicultural competence of future philologists, because the techniques, methods and didactic tools of the English language have a great potential for solving the goals and tasks of multicultural education.

A number of works have been carried out on the methodology of developing and improving the multicultural competence of students, and according to the results of the work, the unique style, advantages and, of course, disadvantages of each method have been noted.

Ruslan Kravets and his team conducted their scientific research on the pedagogical design of the technology of multicultural competence of students in higher educational institutions and expressed their methodical views on improving the multicultural competence of future teachers in their work. . In the course of his experience, he spends on the basis of the developed pedagogical technology of formation of multicultural competence of students, focusing on three target components: conceptual, substantive, procedural. In addition, the study examines changes in the level of multicultural competence of students. According to Kvarets and his team, the implementation of the ideas of multiculturalism has a positive effect on all-round development, fosters tolerance towards other ethnic groups and peoples, serves good neighborly relations, effective conflict resolution, intercultural communication and mutual understanding. Students who have mastered these characteristics fully understand national and universal values and are able to sustainably and constructively cooperate in the modern multicultural world.

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Researcher Jesie Ho-Yin Yau of the University of Gang Kong worked on creating exercises emphasizing the possibility of developing multicultural competence of students through the method of international service.

It should be noted that the diversity of the student body makes higher education unique and creates challenges for student affairs professionals. These groups have different guidelines that the student affairs staff should follow.

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